

The World Health Organization's National Health Simulation Exercise Programme

A COORDINATED APPROACH TO SIMULATION EXERCISES IN HEALTH EMERGENCIES MANAGEMENT EXPONENTIALLY INCREASES AN INSTITUTION'S OR ORGANIZATION'S OR COUNTRY'S EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE CAPABILITIES.

TEXT COUNTRY SIMULATION EXERCISES AND REVIEW UNIT (CER), HEALTH SECURITY PREPAREDNESS (HSP) DEPARTMENT, WHO EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS (WPE) DIVISION, WHO HEALTH EMERGENCIES (WHE) PROGRAM, WHO HQ PHOTO WHO

WHAT ARE SIMULATION EXERCISES IN HEALTH EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS?

Simulation Exercises within health emergencies management are a form of practice or training that models a real-life emergency to which health emergencies simulate response to a fictitious public health event. Simulation exercises are used by countries to develop staff competencies and test established emergency preparedness and response plans and procedures. Simulations are like drills done by institutions or firemen in preparation for fires and other emergencies.¹

"A fire drill is a method of practicing the evacuation of a building for a fire or other emergency. Regularly practicing fire drills helps build muscle memory among the occupants so that they can quickly evacuate without thinking in a real emergency. The practice is rooted in a serious commitment to safety and is an integral part of an organization or building's overall fire safety protocol. It ensures that all individuals are prepared, aware, and capable of taking appropriate actions should an actual fire emergency occur. Regular drills can increase the effectiveness of the actual evacuation in a real crisis, potentially saving lives." Syed Mubashir²

COUNTRY-LED SIMULATION EXERCISES: HISTORICAL EVOLUTION

The WHO Country Simulation Exercises and Reviews (CER) Unit of the Health security Department (HSP) published the WHO Simulation Exercises Manual in 2016 to guide Member States to conduct simulation exercises to build their IHR

capacities.¹ The WHO CER Unit has supported countries globally to conduct over 225 simulation exercises on all hazards from 2016 to date.³

LIMITATIONS OF THE EXISTING COUNTRY-LED SIMULATION EXERCISE PROGRAMME

Countries often conduct simulation exercises for health emergencies preparedness in an ad hoc manner. Moreover, simulation exercises are not evenly done to test different IHR (2005) capacities.⁴ Furthermore, published literature reports suboptimal implementation of recommendations that arise from simulation exercises.⁵ Simulation exercises are a voluntary component of the International Health Regulations Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (IHR MEF). However, the IHR MEF recommends that for a simulation exercise to be considered as part of the IHR (2005) monitoring and evaluation process, a minimum set of information should be shared with WHO.⁶ But inconsistent reporting regarding the number, scope and other details regarding simulation exercises conducted by Member States limits a comprehensive evaluation of the contribution of Simulation Exercises to health emergency management.³

WHAT IS A NATIONAL HEALTH SIMULATION EXERCISE PROGRAM (NHSEP)?

An NHSEP is a coordinated programme of simulation exercises that covers the entire health sector and ensures the effective testing and validation of health systems as part of the emergency preparedness process. The CER Unit of the HSP developed a new guidance, *The WHO*

*Guidance on Implementing a National Health Simulation Exercise Programme (NHSEP) to address the limitations of the currently existing country-led simulation exercise program.*⁷

HOW WILL A NATIONAL HEALTH SIMULATION EXERCISE PROGRAM ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES OF THE EXISTING COUNTRY-LED SIMULATION EXERCISE PROGRAM?

Whereas simulation exercises are conducted in an ad hoc manner, the NHSEP encourages countries to develop and deliver a simulation exercise plan over a 2–5-year period to build capacity within its health system. Repeated practice results in skillful, swift and steady execution by emergency response personnel.

“Exercises are not one-time events but should be undertaken as part of a carefully designed exercise programme that ensures a common strategic objective is addressed. The exercise programme forms a vital component of the emergency preparedness cycle.” (WHO Simulation Exercise Manual, 2017)⁷

Given that simulation exercises do not cover all IHR capacities nor prepare for every possible emergency scenario, the NHSEP covers simulation exercises of varying scopes and for all capacities within the IHR 2005 as well as other events-specific pillars that are relevant to public health emergency preparedness. Simulation exercises build not only the competencies but also the confidence of emergency response personnel to act when called upon to during public health events.

“Confidence brings clarity in situations where stress and confusion run rampant, where the goalposts can be hard to see through the fog, and where the questions become harder to answer, not easier, as time goes on. Confidence leads to more favourable outcomes, more often. Confidence is competence in the realm of emergency response. A confident team that trusts in its abilities is ready to tackle the confusion and uncertainty of an incident or accident. Finding a clear path forward may seem impossible when things fall apart, but an organization with confidence has the best chance at putting the pieces back together.” Stephen Burgess⁸

*In preparation for the inevitable, firefighters have fire drills...
Healthcare workers at operational level have mass casualty event drills...
Public health officials at program and policy level simulate a response to a fictitious public health emergency in a simulation exercise.*

Because simulation exercises may not always result in improvements in IHR capacities, the NHSEP recommends the monitoring of the exercise schedule, quality of exercises delivered, the uptake of recommendations into policy documents and the administrative performance of the program. The NHSEP also recommends the evaluation of the entire program to determine whether it is fit for purpose. Simulation exercises that do not ultimately improve IHR capacities remain box-checking exercises.

Whilst WHO cannot consistently monitor simulation exercises done by Member States, the NHSEP proposes a minimum reporting template to support the monitoring and evaluation of simulation exercises as a voluntary component of the IHR MEF. Monitoring and evaluation provide feedback on the effectiveness of policies, programs, and services.

WHAT ARE THE POTENTIAL BENEFITS OF A NATIONAL HEALTH SIMULATION EXERCISE PROGRAM?

- Strategic-level coordination of all simulation exercises over a defined period.
- Ensuring adequate resources, funding, and staffing are allocated to simulation exercises.
- Ensuring lessons identified from simulation exercises are disseminated and incorporated into policy and operational practice within the health sector.
- Supporting the sharing of learning from simulation exercises in the wider health community.
- Providing an overview of planned and completed exercises, thereby enabling a staged approach to simulation exercise complexity, and ensuring that relevant risks are regularly tested.
- Testing and validating interoperability with other sectors, such as animal health, disaster management, the military and security services.

NEXT STEPS

The WHO will continue working with WHO Member States and UN family to support the development of IHR (2005) capacities to prevent public health emergencies or mitigate their impact when they occur. It is anticipated that the NHSEP will build resilient health systems for the highest level of public health emergency preparedness and readiness. //

FOR MORE INFORMATION

<https://www.who.int/emergencies/operations/simulation-exercises>

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